

-SUPPLEMENTARY FIGURES-

Multi-locus phylogenetic analyses uncover species boundaries and reveal the occurrence of two new entomopathogenic nematode species, *Heterorhabditis ruandica* n. sp. and *Heterorhabditis zacatecana* n. sp.

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Figure S1 Maximum-likelihood phylogenetic tree reconstructed from the nucleotide sequences of: A) the internal transcribed spacer (ITS) rRNA (*ITS*). A total of 775 nucleotide positions, flanked by primers TW81 and AB28, were analyzed; B) the D2-D3 expansion segments of the 28S rRNA (*D2-D3*). A total of 554 nucleotide positions, flanked by primers D2A and D2B, were analyzed; C) the thin filament (F-actin)-associated protein (*unc-87*) gene. A total of 388 nucleotide positions, flanked by primers *unc87F* and *unc87R*, were analyzed; and D) the calmodulin 1 (*cmd-1*) gene. A total of 584 nucleotide positions, flanked by primers *cmd1F* and *cmd1R*, were analyzed. Accession numbers of the nucleotide sequences used for the analyses are shown in Table S3. Some species could not be included in some phylogenetic reconstructions as not all the sequences are publicly available. Numbers at nodes represent bootstrap values based on 100 replications. Bars represent average nucleotide substitutions per sequence position.

H. zealandica CD2507	ID	34	30	46	46	41	35	42	39	40	24	34	29	29	29	26	31	31	33	31	32	32	31	31	31	31	31	31	31
H. atacamensis MEX-20	ID	26	47	46	43	38	47	47	47	49	33	37	33	33	37	36	41	41	41	41	41	40	40	42	42	43	42	42	42
H. marelatus	ID	48	50	47	42	48	45	48	45	48	28	34	32	32	31	30	37	37	37	37	37	35	36	40	40	40	40	40	40
H. indica LN2	ID	37	49	49	40	50	45	45	45	43	41	47	47	47	50	49	54	54	56	54	54	55	55	50	50	50	50	50	50
H. noenieputensis CD2506	ID	48	49	48	42	45	44	45	47	52	53	50	50	49	48	51	51	51	51	51	51	51	44	44	44	44	44	44	44
H. amazonensis CD2510	ID	27	31	27	27	31	26	33	42	42	38	38	46	47	48	48	48	48	48	48	48	48	41	41	41	41	41	41	41
H. baujardi CD2519	ID	20	19	20	19	20	19	26	35	35	37	37	40	41	46	46	46	46	46	46	46	46	45	45	45	45	45	45	45
H. taysearae	ID	13	18	18	18	18	18	18	18	18	18	18	18	18	18	18	18	18	18	18	18	18	18	18	18	18	18	18	18
H. mexicana	ID	11	39	41	40	40	43	43	44	44	44	44	44	44	44	44	44	44	44	44	44	44	44	44	44	44	44	44	44
H. floridensis CD2503	ID	11	39	41	40	40	43	43	44	44	44	44	44	44	44	44	44	44	44	44	44	44	44	44	44	44	44	44	44
H. megidis CD2518	ID	41	41	41	41	41	41	41	41	41	41	41	41	41	41	41	41	41	41	41	41	41	41	41	41	41	41	41	41
H. downesi CD2508	ID	21	23	23	23	23	23	23	23	23	23	23	23	23	23	23	23	23	23	23	23	23	23	23	23	23	23	23	23
H. georgiana CD2500	ID	26	26	26	26	26	26	26	26	26	26	26	26	26	26	26	26	26	26	26	26	26	26	26	26	26	26	26	26
H. georgiana Hbb	ID	21	22	24	24	25	23	24	24	23	24	24	23	23	23	23	23	23	23	23	23	23	23	23	23	23	23	23	23
H. beicherriana CD2516	ID	2	22	22	21	17	18	18	18	18	18	18	18	18	18	18	18	18	18	18	18	18	18	18	18	18	18	18	18
H. beicherriana H06	ID	21	21	20	15	16	16	16	16	16	16	16	16	16	16	16	16	16	16	16	16	16	16	16	16	16	16	16	16
H. zacatecana MEX-39	ID	0	3	7	8	8	8	8	8	8	8	8	8	8	8	8	8	8	8	8	8	8	8	8	8	8	8	8	8
H. zacatecana MEX-40	ID	3	7	8	8	8	8	8	8	8	8	8	8	8	8	8	8	8	8	8	8	8	8	8	8	8	8	8	8
H. zacatecana MEX-41	ID	6	7	7	7	7	7	7	7	7	7	7	7	7	7	7	7	7	7	7	7	7	7	7	7	7	7	7	7
H. ruandica Rw14_N-C4a	ID	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
H. ruandica Rw18_M-Hr1a	ID	0	19	19	19	19	19	19	19	19	19	19	19	19	19	19	19	19	19	19	19	19	19	19	19	19	19	19	19
H. ruandica Rw18_M-Hr1b	ID	19	19	19	19	19	19	19	19	19	19	19	19	19	19	19	19	19	19	19	19	19	19	19	19	19	19	19	19
H. bacteriophora DE2	ID	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
H. bacteriophora DE6	ID	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
H. bacteriophora EN01	ID	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
H. bacteriophora HP88	ID	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
H. bacteriophora IT6	ID	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
H. bacteriophora PT1	ID	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
H. bacteriophora TT01	ID	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

Figure S6 Pairwise number of nucleotide differences in the sequences of the cytochrome c oxidase I (COI) of different *Heterorhabditis* species. A total of 344 nucleotide positions, flanked by primers HCF and HCR, were analyzed. Accession numbers of gene sequences used are shown in Table S3.

Figure S7 Selected polymorphic regions of the alignment of the ITS region showing the nucleotide positions to differentiate the “*Heterorhabditis bacteriophora*” haplotypes recognized by Dhakal et al., 2020. According to our analyses, all the three haplotypes represent a different *Heterorhabditis* species. In addition, a fourth haplotype, which is represented by *H. ruandica* nematodes, emerged from our analyses. Some strains of the haplotype 2 (UP2A2, 267, 269, 270, 271, 275, and 276) might represent a new species, different than *H. zacatecana* (see also Figure S8). The species represented by haplotype 3 remains to be described. Nucleotide position numbers of rRNA genes are according to the sequences of *C. elegans* N2 (NCBI accession number: MN519140).

Figure S8 Maximum-likelihood phylogenetic tree reconstructed from the nucleotide sequences of the internal transcribed spacer (ITS) rRNA (*ITS*). A total of 791 nucleotide positions, flanked by primers TW81 and AB28, were analyzed. Accession numbers of the nucleotide sequences used for the analyses are shown in Table S3. Numbers at nodes represent bootstrap values based on 100 replications. Bars represent average nucleotide substitutions per sequence position.

		P. laumondii subsp. clarkei BOJ-47T	P. laumondii subsp. laumondii RW-46	P. laumondii subsp. laumondii S12-55	P. laumondii subsp. laumondii TT01T	P. laumondii subsp. laumondii S15-56	P. laumondii subsp. laumondii S14-60	P. kayaii DSM 15194T	P. bodei LJ24-63T	P. kleinii MEX-39	P. kleinii DSM 23513T	P. kleinii S10-54	P. kleinii S9-53	P. kleinii S8-52	P. luminescens subsp. mexicana MEX47-22T	P. luminescence subsp. luminescence ATCC 29999T	P. noenieputensis DSM 25462T	P. caribbeanensis HG29T	P. aegyptia BA1T	P. akhurstii DSM 15138T	P. namnaonensis PB45.5T	P. hainanensis DSM 22397T
P. laumondii subsp. clarkei BOJ-47T	ID	77	77	77	77	77	59	60	54	55	55	55	55	54	45	44	48	47	48	48	46	48
P. laumondii subsp. laumondii RW-46	77	ID	89	89	89	89	58	57	53	54	53	53	53	53	44	44	49	47	47	46	44	45
P. laumondii subsp. laumondii S12-55	77	89	ID	100	97	97	59	58	53	54	53	53	53	53	44	44	49	47	47	46	45	46
P. laumondii subsp. laumondii TT01T	77	89	100	ID	97	97	59	58	53	54	53	53	53	53	44	44	49	47	47	46	45	46
P. laumondii subsp. laumondii S15-56	77	89	97	97	ID	100	58	57	53	54	53	53	53	53	44	44	49	47	47	46	45	46
P. laumondii subsp. laumondii S14-60	77	89	97	97	100	ID	58	57	53	54	53	53	53	53	44	44	49	47	47	46	45	46
P. kayaii DSM 15194T	59	58	59	59	58	58	ID	69	63	65	63	63	63	63	45	45	48	47	47	47	45	47
P. bodei LJ24-63T	60	57	58	58	57	57	69	ID	69	69	69	69	69	69	45	45	48	47	48	48	47	48
P. kleinii MEX-39	54	53	53	53	53	53	63	69	ID	87	88	88	88	88	49	48	46	45	46	45	44	45
P. kleinii DSM 23513T	55	54	54	54	54	54	65	69	87	ID	94	94	94	94	47	48	47	46	47	46	45	45
P. kleinii S10-54	55	53	53	53	53	53	63	69	88	94	ID	100	100	100	47	48	47	46	46	46	45	45
P. kleinii S9-53	55	53	53	53	53	53	63	69	88	94	100	ID	100	100	47	48	47	46	46	46	45	45
P. kleinii S8-52	54	53	53	53	53	53	63	69	88	94	100	100	ID	100	47	48	47	46	46	46	45	45
P. luminescens subsp. mexicana MEX47-22T	45	44	44	44	44	44	45	45	49	47	47	47	47	47	ID	71	46	46	46	45	44	44
P. luminescence subsp. luminescence ATCC 29999T	44	44	44	44	44	44	45	45	48	48	48	48	48	48	71	ID	46	46	46	45	44	45
P. noenieputensis DSM 25462T	48	49	49	49	49	49	48	48	46	47	47	47	47	47	46	46	ID	57	55	51	48	50
P. caribbeanensis HG29T	47	47	47	47	47	47	47	47	45	46	46	46	46	46	46	46	57	ID	57	52	49	51
P. aegyptia BA1T	48	47	47	47	47	47	48	46	47	46	46	46	46	46	46	46	55	57	ID	69	56	61
P. akhurstii DSM 15138T	48	46	46	46	46	46	47	48	45	46	46	46	46	45	45	45	51	52	69	ID	60	69
P. namnaonensis PB45.5T	46	44	45	45	45	45	45	47	44	45	45	45	45	45	44	44	48	49	56	60	ID	61
P. hainanensis DSM 22397T	48	45	46	46	46	46	47	48	45	45	45	45	45	45	44	45	50	51	61	69	61	ID

Figure S9 Pairwise comparison of digital DNA-DNA Hybridization (dDDH) scores (%) of *Photorhabdus* strains. Accession numbers of gene sequences used are shown in Table S3.

H. ruandica

H. zacatecana

Figure S10 Lip region of *H. ruandica* n. sp. and *H. zacatecana* n. sp.